

CRACK PROPAGATION AT A SHARP NOTCH IN PA-GF 30 CHARACTERIZED WITH X-RAY TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents investigations on injection moulded specimens with a sharp centre notch made of polyamide 66 with a mass ratio of 35% of short glass fibre reinforcement (PA-GF35). Undamaged and due to cyclic loading damaged specimens were characterised non-destructively with X-ray techniques. The fibre orientation distribution, as well as the micro- and macro-cracking in the material around the sharp crack, were visualized by means of X-Ray-Refraction-Topography in a SAXS setup. Additionally, the Diffraction-Enhanced-Imaging (DEI) technique at the Synchrotron BESSY II was used to evaluate the SAXS results with much higher spatial resolution. Both methods reveal in good accordance the fibre orientation distribution due to the injection moulding process and the damage mechanism of crack propagation starting at the sharp notch as well as micro cracking beside the macro crack and in the crack tip zone.

1 INTRODUCTION

Short fibre reinforced thermoplastic materials are increasingly used in automotive applications and shall replace safety relevant components. Therefore, concepts and models are needed, which enable to estimate the structural durability during the design process, as it is state of the art for metallic structures. The crack propagation at sharp notches in short glass fibre reinforced polyamide due to uniaxial mechanical loading was investigated by non-destructive X-Ray refraction topography in a small angle X-Ray scattering (SAXS) setup and diffraction enhanced imaging (DEI) at the *BAMline* using synchrotron radiation.

In former investigations [1, 2] at un-notched specimens, the damage process of short glass fibre reinforced polyamide caused by mechanical loading was investigated from starting on the micro cracking level to the incipient crack of mm-dimension. Based on high resolution computer tomography and the X-ray-refraction technique, the inner surface due to micro-cracking at the short fibre ends and the fibre matrix debonding of the filament's skin surface was determined quantitatively [3, 4]. The identified degradation process starts with uniformly distributed micro cracking at the fibre end faces and the fibre matrix debonding of the fibre claddings. Further on, their agglomeration to meso damages in a sub-mm scale occurs and multiple crack growth starts distributed over the material volume [5, 6, 7]. Finally, the total failure occurs at the most critical crack.

In a new project, the crack propagation at a sharp pre-notch was investigated recently [7]. The central question to be answered is: does a crack start at the surface of a sharp pre-notch and propagates straight into the material like in brittle materials or does, in contrast, a considerable plastic zone emerge as is well-known from metallic materials? In the latter case, micro cracking is assumed to appear prior to the physical incident crack. For this purpose, the project partner BOSCH developed a mould to produce specimens with a centre pre-notch of 10 mm × 0.4 mm, corresponding to a notch radius of 0.2 mm. The specimens were produced by injection moulding, which causes a specific fibre orientation distribution in the vicinity of the notch.

During constant amplitude fatigue tests under stress control with the nominal amplitude of 18 MPa, crack propagation could be observed between 10^5 and 10^6 cycles [8]. In a previous study at BOSCH, cracks were detected and monitored by an optical method based on a CCD camera and a set of high performance LED lamps to illuminate the specimen surface.

By accompanying X-ray refraction topography, the fibre orientation distribution and the level of micro cracking was determined according to [3, 4, 5, 6]. Additionally to the laboratory measurements of rather low lateral resolution of about $50 \mu\text{m} \times 1 \text{mm}$, high resolution synchrotron refraction radiographs (spatial resolution $5.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $3.5 \mu\text{m}$) were performed at the BAMline [9, 10, 11]. In this paper, the results of these two different NDT-techniques are compared and the crack propagation process in short fibre reinforced plastics is discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 SAXS – fibre orientation distribution and damage evolution

Figure 1: Experimental set-up of the X-Ray refraction topography with SAXS technique.

X-ray refraction [1] is caused by the effect of deflection at the interface of materials of different refractive index as known from visible light passing glass lenses. In the case of X-rays, the refraction angle is below half a degree and in opposite direction due to the dispersion function of isolators. Hence, Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) technique is used. In the experimental set-up (Fig. 1) a collimated X-ray beam passes the sample. At a fixed angle the refracted signal is measured and additionally a signal proportional to the absorption. A characteristic refraction value C is determined, which is proportional to the surface per volume unit [12], *i.e.*, the internal surface. It can be calculated from the scattered I_R and transmitted I_A intensities and the thickness d of the sample in relation to the zero/offset values (I_{R0} , I_{A0} without sample):

$$C = \left[\frac{I_R/I_{R0} - 1}{I_A/I_{A0}} \right] \cdot \frac{1}{d} \quad (1)$$

The intensity of the refracted beam increases as the difference of the refractive indices of two materials forming an interface increase. Hence, the intensity will be higher for materials with debonded fibres or pores than without. By calibration, the absolute as well as the relative inner surfaces C are measured. In most cases, the relative change is sufficient and used in the further investigations. Scanning the whole area of the sample results in a topographic map of internal surfaces (Fig. 5 and 6). Lambert-Beer's law describes the decrease of transmitted intensity I_A as a function of the linear attenuation coefficient μ and the thickness d of the sample:

$$I_A = I_{A0} \cdot e^{-\mu \cdot d} \quad (2)$$

For several applications, it is practical to normalize equation 1 to $\ln(I_A/I_{A0})$ resulting in the relative specific surface C/μ , independent from variation of the thickness due to non-perfect production.

Figure 2: Calculated refraction function $F(\theta)$ depending on the signal of a single filament $f(\theta)$ and the fibre orientation frequency $g(\theta)$ compared to the measured total refraction $C_m(\theta)$

Each fibre filament acts as a cylindrical lens, scattering perpendicular to its axis. As a function of inclination angle θ (see Fig. 1), it contributes according to $\cos^2\theta$ to the total signal [12]. If the filaments are oriented parallel to the collimation plane, the refraction signal becomes maximal. Hence, the signal is zero when the filaments are oriented perpendicular. Experimentally, this can be evaluated only at fibre bundles and for short fibre materials only as a mean value C_m . Normalized to the maximum value and regarding the total reflection and scattering of the fibre ends the signal can be described as:

$$\frac{C_m(\theta)}{C_m(\theta)_{\max}} = A + (1 - A) \cdot \cos^2(\theta) = f(\theta) \quad (3)$$

A is a parameter taking into account the number of fibre ends per volume, which does not change if the fibre length distribution is identical for different materials. Additionally, the semi-crystalline structure of the matrix causes a small contribution to this offset value. For the fibre orientation analysis, the value A was borrowed from a former investigation [4] of a quite similar material.

The mathematical approach is shown graphically in fig. 2. With the fibre orientation frequency, determined by CT, and the \cos^2 -shaped signal of each fibre filament, the measured refraction value at different inclination angles can be described by an \cos^2 -shaped function. Additionally, the offset value has to be taken in account. Finally, the X-ray refraction measurement is a plain projection of inner surfaces due to the fibre filament orientations caused by the injection moulding process. The mathematical derivation is given in [3, 4, 5]. At this, one of the assumptions is that only a few fibres are oriented in z -direction. This was checked with CT-measurements in [5] resulting in a portion of less than 5%. However, regarding the centre notch specimens the filaments in close vicinity to the notch are oriented in thickness (z) direction. With respect to the whole volume of the specimen, at least 90% of the filaments are oriented in the x - y -plane (see figs. 3 and 4). In this case, the fibre orientation distribution can be assumed in good approximation as an elliptical function [3, 4]. The values of the half-axes are equivalent to the matrix elements a_{11} and a_{22} according to [13]:

$$a_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2(\theta) & 0 \\ 0 & \sin^2(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Finally, if the offset value A is known, the matrix elements in equation 4 can easily be derived from two perpendicular X-ray refraction measurements – one in specimen length and one in perpendicular direction. All values in between are given according to equation 3.

Figure 3: Fibre orientation distribution a_{11} -coefficient, injection along y-direction

Figure 4: Fibre orientation distribution a_{11} -coefficient in 3d illustration, injection along y-direction

The dimensions of the centre notch specimens are 40 mm in width, 250 mm in length, and 3 mm in thickness. Only the surrounding of the centre notch is of high interest and over the total width of 40mm only a length of 11mm was scanned with the SAXS technique. The collimated X-ray beam has a cross section of $1000\mu\text{m}$ in width and $50\mu\text{m}$ in height. The region of interest was scanned with the specimen in perpendicular (fig. 5) and parallel orientation with respect to the collimation plane. Hence, 1:20 or 20:1 scans had to be done on each square millimetre due to the aspect ratio of the X-ray beam. Subsequently, a virtual raster of $2\text{ mm} \times 2\text{ mm}$ was superimposed and a mean value of each 80 values was gained. Hence, on the spot each a horizontal and vertical gained mean value is available to determine the matrix elements according to equation 4. To avoid measurement artefacts at the edge of the specimen, only 18×6 mean values were taken into account. The notch-area was treated in the same way. The result is shown in fig. 3 as coloured 2D plot and in fig. 4 coloured and in 3D. The injection was done from y-direction. Finally, at the edge, the a_{11} value of 0.7 indicates a preferred filament orientation along the length direction y. In contrast, the a_{11} value of 0.3 indicates filaments oriented perpendicular to injection upstream and downstream from the notch.

Figure 5: C_m/μ scan perpendicular 38x220 raster points on the specimen, undamaged

Figure 6: C_m/μ scan perpendicular 38x220 raster points on the specimen, damaged

Figs. 5 and 6 display topographs of the specific refraction value C_m/μ of the undamaged and damaged specimen, respectively. As to be expected according to equation 3, the refraction value downstream from the notch is increased due to the transverse oriented filaments (bright pixels). Thus, upstream from the notch the refraction value is decreased due to a perpendicular filament orientation (dark pixels).

The specimen was fatigue loaded 1.2×10^6 load cycles in a tensile testing machine type Instron 8800 with a nominal stress amplitude of 13 MPa (18 MPa in terms of the cross section without the notch) and a load ratio of $R = 0$. At both sides of the notch, cracks appeared with a length of 8mm (left) and 9mm (right). Both cracks are evident in the X-Ray refraction image (s. fig. 6) and the damaged zone seems to be much wider than it is assumed for fatigue crack propagation (see discussion below).

2.2 DEI principle - example transverse cracking in 0°/90°-CFRP-laminate

Figure 7: Principle of Diffraction Enhanced Imaging (DEI) – refracted light is discriminated by the diffraction characteristics of an analyser crystal.

Figure 8: Imaging transverse cracks in a CFRP-sample – from right to left: 0°/90°-CFRP photograph, DEI at the edge and in the centre of the rocking curve, SAXS-technique.

With DEI, the refracted light at cracks or pores is discriminated by means of an analyser crystal (fig. 7), in contrast to the Small Angle X-ray Scanning (SAXS) technique (fig. 1). A parallel beam of monochromatic X-ray light is mandatory which can be generated with synchrotron radiation and a double-crystal monochromator. The specimen is irradiated by the parallel beam with a cross section of 20 mm × 20 mm. Due to the trigonometric relation of the Bragg-angle and the length of the analyser crystal (here Si (111)), the height of the reflected beam is reduced to 7mm. The analyser crystal can be rotated precisely. If the Bragg-angle is adjusted to the maximum intensity only the un-refracted light complies with the Bragg condition and refracted light is missing. Thus, the cracks are imaged dark. If the analyser angle is adjusted off the Bragg position to the outer edge of the rocking curve, *i.e.*, well beyond the half-width position, only refracted light passes the analyser crystal and the cracks are imaged bright (fig. 7).

The DEI principle is briefly illustrated at example of a tensile loaded 0°/90°-CFRP-specimen in figs. 7 and 8. [11]. Due to the 0°/90°-fibre orientation, the inter fibre failures occur perpendicular to the load direction. The fractured specimen, shown in Fig. 8, was investigated comparatively with SAXS technique and DEI. The DEI images are area-wide and contain 520 by 800 pixels with a pixel-size of 28.8 μm by 28.8 μm. The SAXS images are non-area-wide with a step size of 0.3 mm each in x- and y- direction (horizontal and vertical) and contain 40 by 67 pixels of 2000 μm by 50 μm. The marginal values were omitted in the images due to the width of the X-ray beam of the Kratky collimation. The DEI images have a much higher resolution and visualise that the inter fibre cracks mostly pass the whole width of the specimen. Additionally, the cracks are not straight but rather follow the waviness of the 90°-fibre bundles. With this finding, all crack indications in the SAXS-topography can be assumed as one crack over the whole width of the specimen. The result is a crack density of approximately 1/mm. Counting the cracks of the DEI images gives the same result.

2.3 DEI – applied to the PA-GF35 centre notch specimen

The fatigue cracks at both sites of the centre notch in the PA-GF35 specimen were investigated comparative to the SAXS technique with DEI at the BAMline at BESSY II with monochromatic X-ray synchrotron radiation of 17.5 keV. The following images were assembled from 16 by 5 single frames with a spatial resolution of 5.5μm each. At first, an absorption image was taken without the analyser crystal (fig. 9-A) and subsequently the μ*d-image (proportional $-\ln(I_A)$, see equation 2) was calculated

(fig. 9-B). Thus, high irradiation intensities are imaged dark and a higher contrast is achieved. Beside the two cracks, two bond lines become visible in the vicinity of and above the centre notch, as a consequence of the injection process. Therefore, the density of fibre filaments is reduced beside the centre notch and the image appears bright (fig. 9-A) or more dark (fig. 9-B) at this position due to the chosen contrast. Additionally, the circular reduced thickness caused by the notch insert gets visible.

Figure 9: Absorption image of the centre crack specimen with synchrotron radiation, without analyser crystal, specimen perpendicular. A) X-ray absorption I_A , classical radiography B) $\mu \cdot d$ (proportional $-\ln(I_A)$)

In the next step, refraction images were taken using the analyser crystal adjusted to the outer edge (fig. 10-A, inner surfaces appears bright) and to the maximum (fig. 10-B, inner surfaces appears dark) of the rocking curve. Obviously, the damaged regions are depicted on both sides of the notch. Their length is larger than detected in the absorption contrast. Furthermore, the fibre orientation distribution is imaged in good accordance to the SAXS measurements. Thus, upstream from the centre notch the transverse oriented filaments cause an increased refraction intensity, on the other hand the perpendicular oriented filaments in the region of the downstream side and beside the notch appear with a reduced refraction effect in fig. 10-A.

To complete the characterization, the same specimen was mounted horizontally on the manipulator, *i.e.*, parallel to the plain of the analyser crystal. Again, at first the absorption contrast was measured without the analyser crystal (s. fig. 11-A). As assumed, the fatigue cracks and the bond lines are imaged in the same way. Fig. 11-B depicts the refraction image on the outer edge where the damaged regions around the cracks appear clearly detectable. Fig. 11-C recorded at the maximum of the rocking curve barely reveals the damaged regions. However, the fibre orientation distribution caused by the injection moulding process (injection from the left) is mapped clearly in both refraction images. Comparing the fig. 10-A with 11-B, a complementary bright-dark-distribution is obvious. If the specimen is mounted horizontally all filaments parallel to the specimen's length direction appear bright. In contrast, the perpendicular filaments upstream from the notch appear dark, as to be assumed from equation 3 (fig. 11-B). Finally, the results of the SAXS technique are confirmed.

Figure 10: Transmission image of centre crack specimen with synchrotron radiation, with analyzer crystal, specimen perpendicular. A) X-ray refraction I_R , image at the outer edge of the rocking curve, B) inverse X-ray refraction I_R , image at the centre of the rocking curve at maximum intensity.

Figure 11: Transmission image of centre crack specimen with synchrotron radiation, specimen horizontal. A) X-ray absorption I_A image without analyser crystal, classical radiography, B) X-ray refraction I_R , image with analyser crystal at the outer edge of the rocking curve, C) inverse X-ray refraction I_R , image with analyser crystal at the centre of the rocking curve at max. intensity

Figure 12: Transmission images of the centre crack specimen from both sides of the crack with synchrotron radiation, specimen perpendicular, pixel size $3.5\mu\text{m}$. A) and B) X-ray absorption μ^*d , image without analyzer crystal, C) and D) C/μ – specific X-ray refraction, image with analyzer crystal

Figure 13: Optical micrographs of the centre crack specimen. A) and B) visible path of the crack (at the surface) at both sides of the crack, C) magnified detail in the immediate vicinity of the notch on the right-hand side, D) magnified detail of the crack tip on the right-hand side

In the final step, the damaged areas beside the notch were investigated with a further measurement with a spatial resolution of 3.5 μ m with the DEI technique. Comparative this time the m*d image (s. fig. 12-A and B) is confronted with the specific inner surface C/ μ (s. fig. 12-C and D). Distinctly the damaged area left and right of the notch the refraction image is much larger in length and width compared to the absorption contrast. In contrast to figs. 10 and 11, the circular reduced thickness caused by the notch insert does not get visible, thus (see above) the specific inner surface is independent from the local thickness of the specimen.

Additionally, optical micrographs were recorded from the polished surface of the specimen in the vicinity of the fatigue cracks (s. fig. 13). A zigzag shaped pathway of the crack becomes apparent as it is well known for the crack propagation perpendicular to the fibre orientation [7, 8]. In contrast, neither the absorption nor the refraction images depict a zigzag shaped damage area. Moreover, the density is reduced in vicinity of the physical crack due to the increase of micro porosities. This is especially evident at the edges of the notch (s. fig. 13-C) where the crack is distinct opened.

In contrast, there is a small decrease of the density around the crack tip. However, the increase of the inner surface is evident. In comparison to the dimension of the physical crack tip, the region of inner surfaces is much larger. The crack length on both sides of the notch (left 8mm, right 9mm) is nearly equal to each length of the damaged regions indicated by the refraction images. Regarding the microscope images, the crack at the surface seems to be disconnected in the vicinity of the crack tip (see fig. 13-D). This appears as a diffuse ending of the damaged zone in the refraction image.

3 DISSCUSSION

With the use of X-Ray refraction techniques, thus using the physical effect of the refraction of light at inner surfaces in FRP [1], this class of materials can be investigated very efficiently. Applied to continuous fibre reinforced polymers, the damage evolution due to static and fatigue loading can be determined [11, 12, 14]. In the early stages, the method was also applied to short fibre reinforced polymers and a qualitative understanding of the damage behaviour was reached [2]. If the filaments are mainly distributed in one plane the fibre orientation distribution can be described with an elliptical approach [3, 4] and a quantitative analysis is possible.

The damage evolution near a sharp notch was investigated and compared to the damaging process in a uniform stress state. The sharp notch ($K_{t_n}=9.8$ [8]) causes a stress concentration. Thus, only a limited volume is effected by the degradation process at both sides of the centre notch. Nevertheless, the damaged zone is markedly larger than the visible crack at the surface. Compared to the cleavage fracture, refraction imaging reveals a larger width of the damaged volume which does not follow its zigzag shape. The surface crack is disconnected in the vicinity of the crack tip. However, the refraction images indicate a high density of micro cracking. Thus, the micro damages at the filament ends and claddings run ahead the crack tip as a kind of plastic zone well known from metallic materials. Consequently, the material's behaviour is more plastic than brittle. It is unlikely to assume a pure consolidation of existing micro defects. The glass filament end faces have no sizing and are weakly bonded to the polyamide matrix. However, in former investigations [4, 6], an increase of inner surfaces due to the filament pull out caused by mechanical loading was measured.

Additionally, to the presented specimen, others with shorter crack propagation were investigated. Again, the micro cracking around the crack tip was found and ended there. Thus, a micro cracking due to the mechanical loading has to be assumed. Increased inner surfaces due to manufacturing defects were not detected.

A quantitative determination of the inner surface caused by the mechanical loading was not performed. However, it has to be assumed a much higher inner surface caused by micro cracking than the pure surface of the cleavage fracture can have as this was already shown for un-notched specimens [4, 6]. This is finally the reason for the much higher energy release rate of PA-GF35 compared to the unreinforced polymer This results in a high damage tolerance of this class of materials.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The paper illustrates that it is very effective to visualize porosity of less than 1% of the total volume in polymer matrix composites with X-ray refraction techniques. In contrast, using computed tomography (CT) approaches requires to measure 99% of the undamaged material with a very high precision only to recalculate the 1% porosity. Therefore, the spatial resolution of the CT has to be in a sub- μm scale. Thus, the limited spatial resolution of the SAXS setup is sufficient to characterize the fibre orientation distribution and the micro cracking in the investigated PA-GF35. The DEI-technique with synchrotron radiation quantitatively confirms the SAXS results. The high spatial resolution at the synchrotron setup is a nice to have. However, the access to beamlines is limited. Accompanying non-destructive determination of the damage evolution of fatigue loaded FRPs is much more affordable with a SAXS set-up.

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